

[P-M-613] INHERITED THROMBOPHILIA: INCIDENCE AND IMPACT ON PERINATAL OUTCOME IN SOUTH-WESTERN GREECE

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Introduction: Inherited thrombophilias have been suggested as a possible condition of increased susceptibility to adverse pregnancy outcomes. In our study we evaluated the incidence of inherited thrombophilic factors, in 396 healthy women with spontaneous pregnancy of Greek origin and their association with obstetrical complications.

Methods: Peripheral blood was tested for the factor V Leiden, factor II G20210A, and methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase gene C677T mutation.

Results: In unselected women in Southwest Greece, the heterozygosity for the FV Leiden and prothrombin G20210A mutation was 4.3% and 3.5% respectively, while the incidence of the MTHFR T677T genotype was 15.1%. The risk for early and late pregnancy losses, non severe pre-eclampsia, intrauterine fetal growth retardation, intrauterine death was not increased by any of the thrombophilic factors studied. The presence of FV Leiden/MTHFR T677T double genotype increased significantly the risk for placental abruption (OR 20.6, \pm 95% CI: 2.69-158). The presence of FV Leiden, both as a single and combined defect, increased 6.37 times the risk for placental abruption (95% CI 1.6-25) while the presence of MTHFR T677T genotype both as a single and combined defect increased the risk 3.91 times (95% CI 1.4-11). Women with a previous history of obstetric complications and inherited thrombophilia had significantly increased risk for developing complications in a subsequent pregnancy ($p < .05$).

Conclusions: Our data, strongly support the role of inherited thrombophilic factors in the pathogenesis of placental abruption. The effect of these factors in the development of other obstetric complications attributed to placental vasculopathy is unclear.

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